

The Impact of Order in Preventing Innovation

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ABSTRACT: In education, schools, homes, families, institutions throughout the country and the world, the individual must be neat, punctual, orderly, hardworking, and disciplined. In my work, I analyze the impact of clutter during creation. Throughout history, we have been convinced that chance often defines the entire future of humanity, and great discoveries have not always been associated with the amount of work and dedication invested. Children are prone to clutter, waste, and unrestrained play. Rules do not burden children, and their world is open to all. Children do not know what is possible and what is not and do not understand our stereotypes and regulations. Without rules and laws, society cannot function, but progress and progress into the future always take place when someone deviates from the pattern. All institutions strive for obedience and typification of ways of thinking, which often suffocates the inventive mind. A man who is not trapped by stereotypes finds inspiration and freedom of mind and creation in disorder. In a mess, anything is possible, as in the imagination. Before any discovery in any area of creativity, a “eureka” and a “click” must occur. Materializations thrive after idea and vision. The way to reach these solutions is often inexplicable and unexpected. It requires courage and departure from the rules and boundaries of time and society. People who run the world have the burden of fighting stereotypes. They are often unsupported, misunderstood, ridiculed, and marginalized. Their genius, their freedom is revealed either after death or by a combination of circumstances.

KEYWORDS: clutter, creativity, innovation, creation, discovery

Introduction

Many of the discoveries were accidental, caused by various situations, recognized by the right person, and recorded. Often the people who discovered and created had problems in their environment, all the way to deciding whether to stay alive and refute their discovery or die in the truth. The people who run the world go out of the box because the frame is static. It doesn't allow for strides forward. Every step forward is courage, and only brave and confident individuals have changed the world in the 21st century. In recent times, attempts have been made to encourage creativity, there is talk of nurturing and rewarding giftedness, but realistic microenvironments are not always ideal.

Anything that deviates from the majority is considered strange, abnormal, different, and is still excommunicated, isolated, and fenced off from bold individuals.

Reasons can be of the lowest origin, such as jealousy, envy, and fear on the part of the rulers that some innovation could disrupt the stability and control of the social structure,

The consciousness of the individual, society's consciousness, is controlled by centuries-known methods wrapped in new clothes. The methods are intimidation, ex-communication, isolation, stigmatization, rejection, and punishment. Therefore, many talented and creative individuals, out of fear, stifle their energy, fit into rules, stereotypes, norms, and remain mediocre forever.

The system stifles innovation, and only when the intrinsic motivation and strength of the individual manages to overcome everything are changes possible. The development is not over here either, because the realization requires donors, finances, and if all the predispositions are not realized, many inventions remain unperformed.

Play as creativity

The game is the most autonomous human activity and the most expressive form of children's activity. The game is easy to implement, simple in content, spontaneous, fun, exciting, but most importantly useful for the child's development. development, The child develops memory by playing. and developed through various games.

Freedom of play allows each child to express what he feels: joy, satisfaction, dissatisfaction, laughter, crying, fear, disappointment, success, security, insecurity, need for society, anxiety. Play enriches, liberates, helps, connects, occupies, reveals and the game matures, and develops. The game is the initial interaction with the environment. Play is a child's right. Divergence (organization of behavior in a new way), incompleteness (concise behavior, without reaching a goal), inadequacy (behavior is opposed to a given situation). The game is an autobody activity, it has its own sources of motivation, the process of the game is more important than the outcome of the action. The dominance of means over goals prevails in the game, the absence of immediate pragmatic effects. The game fulfills the private functions of the player: it relieves tension, resolves conflicts, positively regulates physical, mental, and socio-emotional development. The game is performed in a state of optimal motivational tone. It develops in the absence of coercion and threats. The game is in a state of moderate mental tension. It is intrinsically motivated, not prompted by external stimuli, not mandatory. It is spontaneous, it is free from external punishments, it is an end in itself. The game asks the question, "What can I do with this object or person?" The game is not a serious performance of an activity or behavior. The game is free of external rules. It involves active engagement. Childhood and play connect the inner world of the imagination with the imitation of reality and adults. Visualizing, inventing, creating is allowed in the game. There is no stupidity or error in the game. Each event is fun and takes the flow of the game into new dimensions. Children at play can be on the moon, in space underground, at sea, in the depths of the ocean, in the sky, they can fly, change shape and roles. The game is omnipotent and without limits.

Normally

A debatable criterion of mental health as a deviation from normal is widespread. There is a social fear of the notion of the abnormal. It is normal what is socially desirable and acceptable. Normality is equated with mediocrity. Normal behavior must not go beyond the framework imposed by social norms. A person must react predictably to situations in order for the majority to react. A normal person must not have major failures, unpleasant situations of which he is the cause, he must not deviate in behavior, clothing, inclinations.

A normal person conscientiously does her job, obediently does what her superiors tell her, does not dream, does not start work for which she is not sure how it will end. A normal person does not dream like a child and distinguishes reality, possibilities, and knows boundaries. She consults with colleagues and cares about social recognition and status. He doesn't waste time on non-profit jobs, nor does he invest his money in experiments.

The problem of understanding the normal arises when comparing the time, place, culture in which we are - between the peoples of Europe and Asia, America, Africa. Normally there are contradictions when we think about how the notion of what is "normal" behavior changes over historical periods.

Mess

Clutter is identified with the terms: chaos, chance, disorder, untidiness organization, confusion, disorderliness, scattering, disarrange. Man is a being who, to a greater or lesser extent, explores

the environment and the world around him from the microcosm to the macrocosm. All achievements the human race puts into patterns and defines. Man has a need to keep everything under control. It all starts with the birth and the introduction of the rhythm of sleeping, feeding, tracking the length and weight of the newborn.

Looking back at the time scale we notice that individuals who deviated from the rules moved the world, consciousness, and opinion of the masses. The lives of these brave, strong, intelligent people were often not glorious, but even disastrous. Society is a hierarchy and when someone in government does not want to lose the established norm of behavior, habits, fears that ensure the functioning of a particular order. The methods are similar from the first civilizations to the present day. They are intimidation, ex-communication, public shame, isolation, the death penalty, life imprisonment, slavery.

Looking at the macrocosm and the microcosm, a man at the same time notices perfect order and finds and explores formulas by which he wants to substantiate the theory of order, but there is always room to refute the acquired knowledge and add new insights.

In the desire to find an order, a man struggles with his own body structure and nature. The human body is a perfect machine. On the question of perfection, one can always find some "but" which leaves room for what is not clear to us and which does not fit into mathematical purity and order. There is no perfectly healthy man, no perfect beauty, no perfect mind. Disease, mutations, are a warning and a reminder that our structure and environment are too complicated to be described by formulas. Many branches of science have developed, information is growing. We know the DNA structure, we know countless diseases, countless mutations, countless deviations from the set ideal that we have not yet managed to create. The universe is full of surprises and deviations.

Therefore, many inventions and discoveries happen like flashes or clicks in the minds of scientists. Imposing one's will on one's environment and the desire to maintain order and control in any area of life will never be achieved.

The paradox of control provokes rebellion against the controllers themselves: examples include young children, partners, and ourselves, whenever we try to stick to some firm new schedule or habit. The desire to control rising standards is becoming more demanding, and minor control failures are frustrating.

Some people need clutter in order to feel relaxed, free, they do not lose energy to stack, sort because in their energy and rush of research and creation they consider it a waste of time. In his workspace, the creator manages very well and remembers where what and why was left or put away.

Chaos theory is a branch of mathematics that focuses on the study of chaos as dynamic systems whose seemingly random states of disorder and irregularity actually govern fundamental patterns and deterministic laws that are very sensitive to initial conditions. Chaos theory is an interdisciplinary theory that states that within the apparent randomness of chaotic complex systems there are fundamental patterns, interconnectedness, constant feedback loops, repetition, self-similarity, fractals, and self-organization.

Chaotic behavior exists in many natural systems, including fluid flow, heart rate irregularities, weather, and climate. Chaos theory has applications in a variety of disciplines, including meteorology, anthropology, sociology, physics, environmental science, computer science, engineering, economics, biology, ecology, pandemic crisis management, and philosophy. It is a natural state of chaos.

Upbringing and education

The child in the maternity ward becomes a member of society, gets its number. It measures the child's weight and length and enters the system by birth. He is allowed at the earliest age to playtime which is forbidden to him as he grows up and introduces him to a world of obligations

and duties. In the school system, in addition to the necessary knowledge, he has to go through a lot of information while learning, collecting the best grades and diplomas and certificates. Paper is the definition and guarantee of its ability and integration into society and the system.

In the process of schooling, an individual accepts everything and goes through various obstacles, obligations, requirements that are useful, and those that are reminiscent of dressage. At the end of the process, we get almost uniformed holders of a certain profession. A man is fit for a job that will do most of his life.

Any pressure on a person has an adverse effect on work performance, causes stress, and the brain shrinks. Stress adversely affects each individual. One way to cause stress is the process of schooling itself, the struggle for grades, that is, the struggle for survival during employment and the extravagant reward in the form of a monthly income. In the rut of everyday life, man gets tired, overwhelmed with data, accounts have no time to create.

Creativity

In the 21st century, initiatives to awaken creativity are emerging. From uniformed learned people, it is again trying to return them to the state of freedom, the childhood of creation, the age of unfettered creativity. There are creativity awakening courses. The methods on offer range from scientifically tested to fraudsters and laymen.

Defining creativity, different experts end up with the same conclusion. Creativity means the ability to generate something new, for example, unusual ideas, deviations in thinking from stereotypes and traditional schemes, and quick resolution of problematic situations. The ability to be creative or inventive is a useful trait for a person because that trait allows them to adapt to the world around them.

It is believed that creativity is based on divergent thinking, that is, thinking that diverges in several ways. Divergent thinking is triggered when one problem is solved in different ways, each of which can be accurate. Obviously, the multitude of solution options creates the ability to find original ideas.

Our brain is divided, and each half has its own way of cognition, its own special perception of the surrounding reality. Figuratively speaking, each of us has two minds, two consciousnesses, that communicate and cooperate through a connecting “cable” of nerve fibers that extend between the hemispheres.

There is a lot of research-based on examining the brains of people who are characterized as creative people. The left and right hemispheres of creative people are better connected, the flow of information is freer, and people do not separate logic, reality, norms from their ideas of imagination and the desire to reproduce the imagined.

Creativity always contains originality, i.e. something new, unusual, and unused in a way known until then. If we reduce all definitions of creativity to a "common denominator", we get constant determinants of creativity: creating or proposing something partially or completely new, creating an existing object with new properties or characteristics, imagining new possibilities that no one has yet designed, looking at or performing something completely a different way from the way previously considered normal or possible and the like.

We know little about how the brain actually works, our evolutionary history tells us this: A brain designed to solve problems related to survival in an unstable external environment, and doing so in almost constant motion. Learning from mistakes so that we could survive in large expanses also meant paying attention to some things to the detriment of others, and it meant creating a memory in a special way. Today, medicine offers a complete assessment: "Although we have been forcibly pushing our brains into classrooms and booths for decades, our brains are actually designed to survive in the jungle, not in offices."

Unconscious cognition is the processing of perception, memory, learning, thinking, and language without us being aware of it.

The role of the unconscious mind in decision-making is a topic widely discussed by neuroscientists, linguists, philosophers, and psychologists around the world. Although the actual level of involvement of the unconscious brain during the cognitive process could still be a matter of differing opinion, the fact that the unconscious brain plays a role in cognitive activities is undeniable.

Creation

Creation is present in all areas of human life. The difference in approach characterizes what man creates. Multiplication, the production of an individual product meets the limits of the majority and their reach is in the accumulation and making of capital. After new discoveries, the production system changes, and production continues while demand is in the market.

The higher form of creation encompasses the intriguing motivation of individuals who invest their energy in research, exploration, the search for new ideas and discoveries. Such a way of thinking is possessed by unrestrained children and a creative mind. The difference between the commercial release of products in addition to financial gains is that creative creation does not bring wealth in material and economic. Creativity, unrestrainedness, clutter are the state of nature and children's games.

Coincidence of discovery

Life brings everyone unforeseen situations, problems. The difference in perceptions of problems and differences characterizes the personality and the way a person will develop and whether they will progress. The creative person in the problem sees a challenge, fun, the possibility of research. Strange and abnormal to the creative mind is not a negative connotation, but an opportunity for discovery, idea, and inspiration. Natural laws happen to everyone, but only geniuses recognize them in an instant. It is necessary to make a mess in the creation.

The definition of disorder refers not only to scattered things in the environment but also to concepts such as street riots, messy life, etc. Any deviation from the majority and a desire for change causes disorder in its area. Excessive desire for control, burdening with rules, levies, taxes, obligations leads to a crackdown, causes the opposite effect and a mess, revolution, change occurs.

The discovery is made by people who are curious about the new and dissatisfied with the status quo. These are people who are curious and who ask old questions in new ways and who ask new questions. Inventions are created by curious people dissatisfied with current methods and means of work. These are people who are looking for something more than gradual improvement in the usual way of working. Innovation is born of dissatisfied people looking for new opportunities behind doors that most people believe are closed.

“Coincidence” is often applied to discoveries and inventions made by chance rather than with intent. Examples in all segments of human existence are Nobel, Pasteur, Archimedes, Newton, Einstein, Fleming. Random discoveries stem from the convergence of preparation, ability, and desire.

Conclusions

Children are unfettered, free, unencumbered. Until society and parenting systems take children into their molds, children are not afraid of mistakes, they are not ashamed, they are not afraid of stupidity, they are not condemning, they are not judging. Children do whatever comes to mind. Growing up, many lose the natural property of creative thinking, accept molds, stereotypes, accept themselves as a personality type, do not dare to step out of the zone of comfort and mediocrity. Creatives, researchers, scientists do not succumb to the pressures of mediocrity,

overcome various obstacles, do not give up, listen to their impulse to create, follow their curiosity and desire to explore and discover.

Free creative people change the material and social world. They follow their visions, see new laws that touch us all. They notice deviations, discover existing laws, recognize coincidences. With an open fearless mind, they follow their intuition, drive their inner motivation, are not afraid, do not accept boundaries, and move the world. Encouraging already stifled creativity is a pale copy of the true potential that children innately have in their free world of imagination, vision, ideas, and unencumberedness.

Selective References

- Beitman, B.D. 2009. "Coincidence Studies: A Freudian Perspective." *PsycCRITIQUES* 55(49): Article 8.
- Cambray, J. 2005. "The place of the 17th century in Jung's encounter with China." *Journal of Analytical Psychology* 50(2):195-207.
- Greene, Liz. 2018. *Jung's Studies in Astrology: Prophecy, Magic, and the Qualities of Time*. Milton: Routledge.
- Jung, C. 1969/2012. *Synchronicity: An Acausal Connecting Principle*. Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. 1977. *Jung on Synchronicity and the Paranormal: Key Readings*. London: Routledge.
- Main, Roderick. 2000. "Religion, science and synchronicity." *Harvest: Journal for Jungian Studies* 46(2): 89-107.
- Morrison, P.D., and Murray, R.M. 2009. "From Real-World Events to Psychosis: The Emerging Neuropharmacology of Delusions." *Schizophrenia Bulletin* 35(4): 668-674.
- Prazer, B., and Charles Fishman. 2015. *A Curious Mind: The Secret to a Bigger Life*. New York, NY: Simon & Schuster.
- Tarnas, R. 2006. *Cosmos and Psyche: Intimations of a New World View*. New York: Penguin Group.
- Tart, C. 1981. "Causality and Synchronicity: Steps towards Clarification." *Journal of the American Society for Psychical Research* 75 (April 1981): 121-41.
- Thoreau, H.D. 2004. "Walking." In *The Making of the American Essay*, edited by John D'Agata, 167–95.
- Van Elk, M., Friston, K. and Bekkering, H. 2016. "The Experience of Coincidence: An Integrated Psychological and Neurocognitive Perspective." *The Challenge of Chance*. The Frontiers Collection. pp. 171–185.
- Wilson, R.A. 1988. *Coincidence: A Head Test*. Phoenix, AZ: Falcon Press.